

APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES IN HISTORY EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article discusses the possibilities of using artificial intelligence technologies in training future historians. As you know, the most popular artificial intelligence chatbot currently is the ChatGPT application. Unfortunately, access to this service for users from Russia and Belarus is currently limited. However, there are many third-party applications free from such restrictions that use the ChatGPT API and solve similar problems. The article analyzes three of the most interesting and useful of these services: Phind.com - a search engine for researchers, Talkai.info - a service that provides access to ChatGPT in Russian, Explainlikeimfive.io - an application that explains complex concepts and concepts. Examples are given of the use of the above services in planning, organizing and conducting the educational process at the faculty that trains historians. It is shown that the rapid development of artificial intelligence technologies will lead to a radical change in approaches to organizing the educational process, its structure and content. According to some experts, by the end of 2026, ninety percent of the content on the Internet will be generated by artificial intelligence. This cannot but affect educational content posted on the Internet. In conclusion, it is noted that, unfortunately, solutions obtained using deep neural networks are often impossible to verify. This naturally reduces their value. That is why it is still difficult to judge how the widespread introduction of artificial intelligence technologies will affect the quality of specialist training.

Keywords: artificial intelligence, learning, history, Chat GPT, search for developers, open access, clarification of concepts, Polotsk, Polotsk State University, scientific search.

On November 30, 2022, OpenAI opened free access to its main development - a chatbot with artificial intelligence that works in conversational mode. The bot was called ChatGPT (English Generative Pre-trained Transformer or Russian generative pre-trained transformer). ChatGPT quickly attracted attention with its extensive capabilities for writing code, creating original texts, generating plans and scripts, etc., showing the creativity characteristic of natural intelligence. The bot's popularity grew, and two months after its launch, in early February 2023, the number of its active users reached 100 million people. A historical record was set for growth rate and number of visitors. In Russia and Belarus, access to the service is limited. However, the high popularity of the service has led to the emergence of a significant number of third-party applications that use the ChatGPT API for their work and solve similar problems. It is precisely such applications that we will consider in this work. We analyzed more than 30 software products and settled on the following three applications.

Phind.com is a search engine that uses artificial intelligence and a ChatGPT interface to efficiently search for information. The creators of the Phind.com resource position it as a search engine for developers. Figure 1 shows the Phind.com home page.

Picture-1. Home page of the search engine phind.com The resource has a laconic design.

In the center of the screen is a large rectangular box that says “Ask anything.” The text of the request is entered into this field. Below the field for entering a search query there are three switches that allow you to select the search mode. Turning on the first switch, “Expert,” puts the system into expert search mode. The most powerful search model is used, and the waiting time for a response increases as the search speed decreases. When you turn on the “Concise” mode, the answer will be more concise, but faster. The “Creative” mode includes the generation of a response by the system’s own artificial intelligence, without using Web search results. The system remembers the current user and stores his history (or Thread) of requests. You can manage requests using the menu located on the right side of the screen. The menu has three items: “New Thread”, “Clear Threads” and “Customize search”. The first menu item allows you to create a new thread, the second allows you to clear all threads, and the third allows you to rank search results. Filters, which are used for ranking, provide the user with the opportunity to select a language, include/exclude a group of domains from the search, include/exclude individual sites or groups of sites from the search, etc.

At the same time, as our experience with the resource has shown, the best results are obtained if English is used as the search language. We would like to draw the attention of readers to the fact that queries and answers to them were translated using the Google Translate service. We have not edited the translations. The application's spelling has been preserved. In all of the examples below, user requests will be in bold and system responses will be in italics.

Query: **How to use ChatGPT in a Latin course?**

1st option. All search mode switches are in the “Off” position.

System response:

To use ChatGPT in a Latin course, students can use the tool in several ways. ChatGPT is a chatbot from OpenAI that allows users to “talk” to it in a way that simulates natural conversation. With a deep understanding of the features, limitations, and risks associated with generative AI, it becomes a powerful tool for saving time and energy. Here are some ways to incorporate ChatGPT into coursework: (<https://www.coursera.org/articles/chatgpt>)
1. One of the most exciting uses of ChatGPT for students is as a tool for identifying simpler or alternative ways to solve complex course problems. For example, ChatGPT has a huge

collection of shortcuts and techniques for solving a wide range of complex ST EM problems. From basic physics and mathematics to complex engineering problems, ChatGPT can provide simpler and proven ways to solve complex problems and find accurate solutions with much less effort. Students can ask ChatGPT for a quick way to solve a problem, and the AI chatbot will generate results. However, students should always clarify whether the abbreviation applies to all cases of the problem. If a student has a preferred method that makes learning easier for them, ChatGPT can help present complex problems in a way that makes it easier for them to understand. (<https://medium.com/geekculture/how-to-use-chatgpt-for-teaching-9b2237bdfc67>)

2nd option. The "Expert" switch is in the "On" position, the other two switches are in the "Off" position.

System response:

To use ChatGPT in a Belarus history course, you can use the AI model to provide detailed explanations, summaries, and answers to questions related to various historical periods and events in Belarus. Here are several approaches to integrating ChatGPT into the classroom: Summarizing historical periods or events: Use ChatGPT to create short summaries of specific periods, such as the BSSR from 1945 to 1990, the Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, or the period of Alexander Lukashenko. Generating historical context: ChatGPT can help provide context for specific events, such as the Chernobyl tragedy. Answering student questions: Use ChatGPT to answer student questions about the history of Belarus. Create history quizzes or tests: Create quizzes or tests based on course content to assess student understanding of the material.

3rd option. Explainlikeimfive.io

The Explainlikeimfive.io service is designed to explain complex concepts in simple and accessible language. 29 languages are supported, including Russian, so all dialogues with the system can be conducted in Russian. The home page of this resource is shown in Figure 3.

Picture 3. Home page of the explainlikeimfive.io service

In the center of the screen, under the image of an owl, there is a query input field asking you to start a dialogue. Just above, to the right of the owl, there is a drop-down menu that allows you to select the dialogue language. Below the input field is another drop-down menu offering to set the response level. There are four such levels:

I'm FEELING Pretty Dumb – Я ЧУВСТВУЮ себя довольно глупым

I'm FEELING Dumb – Я ЧУВСТВУЮ себя глупым

I'm FEELING Smart – Я ЧУВСТВУЮ себя умным

I'm FEELING Pretty Smart – Я ЧУВСТВУЮ себя довольно умным

The thoroughness and detail of the answer depends on the selected level. To the right of the input field is the "SARCASM" switch. The emotional coloring of the response depends on whether it is turned on or not.

RAM (Random Access Memory) is a type of computer memory that is used for temporary storage of data and program instructions, while ROM (Read Only Memory) is a type of computer memory that is used for permanent storage of data and programs. Instructions. Other generators work similarly. Let us now consider the capabilities of the system in the EMAILRESPONSE GENERATOR mode. Figure 6 shows the screen view of a system operating in this mode.

Conclusion

As follows from all of the above, the rapid development of artificial intelligence technologies will undoubtedly lead to a radical change in approaches to organizing the educational process, its structure and content. According to some experts by the end of 2026, ninety percent of the content on the Internet will be generated by artificial intelligence. This cannot but affect educational content posted on the Internet. It will become more meaningful and dynamic, since the time and effort required to create it will be significantly reduced. In conclusion, we note that throughout its more than half a century of history, neural networks have already experienced both periods of rapid growth and increased attention, as well as periods of skepticism and indifference. Today they are back in the spotlight thanks to the development of a family of unsupervised pre-learning algorithms and the success of deep neural networks in practical problems such as speech and image recognition. However, it should be borne in mind that solutions obtained using deep. neural networks are often impossible to verify. This

can mislead gullible users and lead to serious errors in decision making. There will almost certainly be problems that neural networks can handle poorly. All this must be taken into account when organizing training and working with neural networks.

References:

- 1.Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). GENDER DIFFERENTIATION OF MASCULINE AND FEMININE VERBALIZATION. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(05), 59-65.
- 2.Djalilova, Z. O. (2021). Studies on gender linguistics in the field of Uzbek language. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(3), 391-397.
- 3.Obidovna, D. Z., & Denis, S. (2021). Formulas of speech etiquette in a gender-engineered communication strategy. *Central asian journal of theoretical & applied sciences*, 2(6), 5-11.
- 4.Obidovna, D. Z. (2021). Comparative Analysis Of Uzbek Men's And Women's Speech Through The Prism Of Gender Linguistics. *Central Asian journal of literature, philosophy and culture*, 2(2), 22-26.
- 5.Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). Speech Behavior and its Gender Specificity on the Basis of the Main English Language Variants. *Middle European Scientific Bulletin*, 22, 199-205.
- 6.Obidovna, D. Z. (2021). Gender issues in foreign theoretical linguistics: concerning the history of the issue. *Gender issues*, 7(6).
- 7.JALILOVA, Z. O. (2021, March). ON THE FORMATION OF THE LANGUAGE OF SCIENTIFIC LITERATURE IN THE HISTORY OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 18-22).
- 8.Jalilova, Z. O. (2020). Concerning the issue of terms, having a place with various morphological classes (in view of the example of the terminological arrangement of social action). *Новый день в медицине*, (4), 501-503.
- 9.Djalilova, Z. O., Juraev, S. S., & Kosimov, S. M. (2021). LATIN AS A PROFESSIONAL LANGUAGE OF MEDICAL WORKERS. *Международный научно-практический электронный журнал «МОЯ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНАЯ КАРЬЕРА»*. Выпуск № 23 (том 1)(апрель, 2021). Дата выхода в свет: 30.04. 2021., 79.
- 10.Джалилова, З. О., Хасанов, К. А., & Султонов, А. А. (2021). Роль научного управления в процессе обучения высококвалифицированных врачей в новом Узбекистане. *Молодой ученый*, (26), 377-379.
- 11.Dzhalilova, Z. O. (2021). The Latin language's international status. *Молодой ученый*, (41), 32-34.
- 12.Dzhalilova, Z. O., & Mirfajziev, K. (2021). Latin as the language of medicine. *Молодой ученый*, (41), 35-37.
- 13.Dzhalilova, Z. O., Izomova, S. G., & Ahmedova, G. A. (2021). Intercultural communication and the Latin language. *Молодой ученый*, (24), 398-400.
- 14.Dzhalilova, Z. O. (2021). History of formation of Latin language. *Молодой ученый*, (41), 34-35.
- 15.Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). GENDER SPEECH BEHAVIOR IN THE CONTEXT OF THE SOCIO-LINGUISTIC FACTOR. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(6), 190-198.
- 16.Dzhalilova, Z. O., Hajdarova, N. S., & Tashpulatova, N. A. (2021). Latin in the Contemporary World. *Молодой ученый*, (24), 400-402.

17. Djalilova, Z. (2022). POLITENESS IN WOMEN'S DISCOURSE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Academic research in modern science*, 1(11), 29-34.
18. Джалилова, З. (2022). РЕАЛИЗАЦИЯ МАКСИМ ВЕЖЛИВОСТИ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ДИАЛОГАХ. *Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot*, 1(21), 22-33.
19. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). A Speech Etiquette Formula for the Gender Communication Strategy. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(10), 44-50.
20. Djalilova, Z. (2022). DISCURSIVE ELEMENTS AND THE CATEGORY OF POLITENESS. *Academic research in modern science*, 1(12), 8-14.
21. Джалилова, З. О. (2022). НУТҚ ҲАРАКАТЛАРИДА ХУШМУОМАЛАЛИКНИНГ ГЕНДЕР ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 5(5).
22. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). DISTINCTIVE FEATURES OF MALE AND FEMALE ORAL SPEECH IN MODERN ENGLISH. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 2(10), 14-21.
23. Obidovna, D. Z. (2022). THE MAIN CONCEPTS OF POLITENESS IN MODERN LINGUOPRAGMATICS: THE POLITENESS PRINCIPLE BY J. LEECH. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 2(11), 15-20.
24. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER DIFFERENTIATION OF DISCOURSE ELEMENTS AS INDICATORS OF POSITIVE AND NEGATIVE EVALUATIONS. *International Bulletin of Applied Science and Technology*, 2(12), 55-63.
25. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER-DETERMINED DIFFERENCES IN THE SPEECH OF LITERARY CHARACTERS. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(12), 210-215.
26. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER ELEMENT OF SPEECH BEHAVIOR FROM THE POSITION OF TEXT ORGANIZATION MECHANISMS. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 2(13), 274-281.
27. Джалилова, З. (2022). ПРАГМАТИЧЕСКИЙ ВЗГЛЯД НА МЕЖЛИЧНОСТНОЕ ОБЩЕНИЕ. *Zamonaviy dunyoda ilm-fan va texnologiya*, 1(7), 331-336.
28. Djalilova, Z. (2022). GENDER XUSHMUOMALALIKKA ASOSLANGAN IBORALARNING SHAKLLANISHI. *Zamonaviy dunyoda innovatsion tadqiqotlar: Nazariya va amaliyot*, 1(28), 303-308.
29. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & SHARIPOV, A. G. ALPHABET OF LATIN LANGUAGE. *МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый"*, (52), 338-339.
30. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & UBAJDULLOEV, A. U. U. COMPARISON DEGREES OF ADJECTIVES IN LATIN LANGUAGE. *МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый"*, (52), 336-338.
31. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & JAKUBOV, U. S. NUMBERS IN LATIN LANGUAGE. *МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый"*, (52), 339-341.
32. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & ALIEV, M. N. ADJECTIVE IN LATIN LANGUAGE. *МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый"*, (52), 332-334.
33. DZHALILOVA, Z. O., & ALIEV, M. N. PRONOUNS IN LATIN LANGUAGE. *МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый"*, (52), 334-336.
34. DJALILOVA, Z. O., & KHAYOTOV, K. M. K. U. LATIN PRONOUNS. *МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый"*, (53), 257-258.
35. DJALILOVA, Z. O., & KHAYOTOV, M. K. U. VERBS IN LATIN LANGUAGE. *МОЛОДОЙ УЧЕНЫЙ Учредители: ООО" Издательство Молодой ученый"*, (53), 255-257.

- 36.Djalilova, Z. O. (2023). A DISCOURSIIVE TURN IN THE THEORY OF LINGUISTIC POLITENESS: TO THE FORMATION OF THE THEORY OF LINGUISTIC IMPOLITENESS. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(02), 15-23.
- 37.Djalilova, Z. (2023). PEDAGOGICAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGY: ESSENCE, CHARACTERISTICS AND EFFICIENCY. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(23), 29-38.
- 38.Djalilova, Z. (2023). THE SIGNIFICANCE AND POSITION OF TEACHING METHODS IN PROFESSIONAL TRAINING. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 2(10), 31-42.
- 39.Djalilova, Z. (2023). THE USE OF LATIN TERMINOLOGY IN MEDICAL CASE. *Академические исследования в современной науке*, 2(14), 9-15.
- 40.Джалилова, З. (2023). The notion of illocution in the theory of speech acts by John Austin. *Современные тенденции при обучении иностранному языку в XXI веке*, 1(1).
- 41.Obidovna, D. Z. (2023). ADAPTING TEACHING METHODS TO MODERN EDUCATIONAL TRENDS: PEDAGOGICAL ASPECT. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 3(10), 72-77.
- 42.Djalilova, Z. (2023). LANGUAGE LEARNING STRATEGIES AND THEIR IMPLICATION FOR TEACHING ENGLISH. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(11), 18-22.
- 43.Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaimonovich, D. S. (2023). Influence of the Mode of Work and Recreation of the Student's Health. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF HEALTH SYSTEMS AND MEDICAL SCIENCES*, 2(3), 3-5.
- 44.Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2023). Forming a Healthy Lifestyle for Students on the Example of the Volleyball Section in Universities. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 3(3), 22-25.
- 45.Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). Physical activity and its impact on human health and longevity. *Достижения науки и образования*, 2 (82), 120-126.
- 46.Obidovna, D. Z., & Sulaymonovich, D. S. (2022). THE CONCEPT OF "HEALTHY LIFESTYLE" IN PSYCHOLOGICAL RESEARCH. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 3(06), 53-64.
- 47.Jo'rayev, S., & Djalilova, Z. (2022). NEUROLOGICAL STATUS OF CHILDREN WITH INTRAUTERINE DEVELOPMENTAL DELAY. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 2(9), 34-37.
- 48.Djalilova, Z. (2023). ADVANCING PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES: LEVERAGING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES TO ENHANCE THE INTEGRATION OF ENGLISH AND LATIN LANGUAGE INSTRUCTIONAL METHODS. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(12), 54-60.
- 49.Djalilova, Z. (2023). ADVANCING CRITICAL THINKING PROFICIENCY THROUGH OPTIMIZED PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES. *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(12), 61-67.
- 50.Djalilova, Z. (2023). IMPROVING METHODOLOGIES FOR INTEGRATIVE ENGLISH AND LATIN LANGUAGE TEACHING USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES. *Центральноазиатский журнал образования и инноваций*, 2(12 Part 2), 29-34.
- 51.Djalilova, Z. (2023). ELEVATING CRITICAL THINKING WITH EFFICIENT TEACHING METHODS (GEARED TOWARDS MEDICAL STUDENTS). *International Bulletin of Medical Sciences and Clinical Research*, 3(11), 97-102.

- 52.Obidovna, D. Z. (2023). THE ART OF QUESTIONING: ENHANCING CRITICAL THINKING THROUGH EFFECTIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNIQUES. *International Journal Of Literature And Languages*, 3(11), 54-60.
- 53.Djalilova, Z. O., Tasheva, N. Z., Nematova, Z. T., & Nasrieva, G. Z. (2023). LEXICO-SEMANTIC PECULIARITIES IN MODERN ENGLISH (ANALYZING ITS BOTH LANGUAGE VARIANTS: BRITISH AND AMERICAN ENGLISH ONES). *Journal of Advanced Zoology*, 44(S2), 4433-4445.
- 54.Rasulov, Z. I. (2023). COMPARATIVE STUDY OF LINGUISTIC PHENOMENA OF A NATIONAL-CULTURAL NATURE, REPRESENTING MYTHOLOGICAL LINGUISTIC UNITS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES, 2(20), 19-24.
- 55.Rasulov, Z. I. (2023). THE NOTION OF NON-EQUIVALENT WORDS AND REALIAS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education, Social Science & Humanities*, 11(6), 35-40.
- 56.Rasulov, Z. (2023). LISONIY TEJAMKORLIKNING AXBOROT IFODASIDAGI ORTIQCHALIKKA MUNOSABATI. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz), 42(42).
- 57.Rasulov, Z., & Artikov, A. (2023, May). THE PRINCIPLE OF REDUNDANCY IN COMPOUND SENTENCES. In *Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes* (pp. 1-4).
- 58.Rasulov, Z. (2023). The principle of cognitive economy as an important factor in information transmission. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz), 42(42).
- 59.Rasulov, Z. (2023). ПРИНЦИПЫ ЭКОНОМИИ ФОНАЦИОННОЙ ЭНЕРГИИ. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz), 42(42).
- 60.Rasulov, Z. (2023). PEDAGOGIKA VA PSIXOLOGIYADA MANIPULYATSIYA TUSHUNCHASI. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.uz), 39(39).
- 61.Olimjonovna, K. O. (2023). AYOLLARDA REPRODUKTIV TIZIM FAOLIYATINING O'ZGARISHIDA GIPOTERIOZ BILAN BIRGA KECHISHI. *Ta'lim innovatsiyasi va integratsiyasi*, 10(3), 174-179.

